

**Diffusion of Pulsars in the $P - \dot{P}$
diagram: study of stochastic
pulsar timing noise models**

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Abstract

Pulsar evolution in the period-period derivative ($P - \dot{P}$) plane is the defining empirical characteristic of the dynamics of the pulsar population. Pulsars exhibit deviation from the typical spin-down due to a non-deterministic phenomenon: timing noise. Understanding timing noise in pulsars is crucial for the physical conception of the interior of neutron stars and high-precision experimentation. We study two stochastic models which describe the typical spin-down by electromagnetic braking law with additive noise in the torques at work in a neutron star. In the minimal version, a neutron star is considered to be rotating rigidly, and the Power Spectral Density (PSD) obtained depicts the ubiquitous Brownian motion. An extension of the model is considered in which the white noise driver in second order derivative of angular frequency $\ddot{\nu}(t)$, generates red noise in phase $\phi(t)$, angular frequency $\nu(t)$, and first-order derivative of angular frequency $\dot{\nu}(t)$ and the corresponding analytical and numerical PSDs are calculated which are consistent and justify the result. The work focuses on building a numerical routine that can be utilized in the future for more refined models with statistical features that can only be estimated numerically.

Contents

1	Introduction	4
1.1	Discovery of Pulsars	4
1.2	Dynamics of Pulsars	5
1.2.1	Energy Loss due to Rotations	5
1.2.2	Magnetic fields and dipole radiation	6
1.2.3	Power law and braking index	7
1.3	$P - \dot{P}$ diagram	8
1.4	Timing Noise	9
2	Stochastic models for timing noise	10
2.1	Deterministic and stochastic torques	11
2.1.1	Brownian Model	13
2.1.2	The recent Vargas and Melatos stochastic model	15
2.2	Power Spectral Density	17
3	Numerical simulations of the Brownian and Vargas models	19
3.1	Brownian Model	19
3.2	Vargas Model	21
4	Conclusions	26
5	Prospects	27
	Appendix	28

List of Figures

1	We plot the $P - \dot{P}$ diagram for about 2000 known pulsars listed in the ATNF catalogue. The lines of constant τ are in red, and the lines of constant B are in blue. Pulsars part of a binary system are not plotted.	9
2	The angular velocity of the Vela pulsar (left) and the pulsar J0942-5552 (right) vs time. The parameters used to generate the plots have been listed in Table 1.	20

3	The power spectral densities of the Vela pulsar (left) and the pulsar J0942-5552 (right). The red line is a reference line of slope -2. The dashed black lines indicate the observational window: $\nu_0 = 2\pi/(20 \text{ yr})$, and $\nu_s = 2\pi/(1 \text{ day})$. The parameters used to generate the plots have been listed in Table 1.	21
4	Actual (left) and few random realizations of the generated (right) timing residuals of the pulsars. Top panel shows the data corresponding to the pulsar J0942-5552 and the bottom panel corresponds to the Vela pulsar. The real data has been extracted from Vargas and Melatos (2023) and Antonelli et.al (2023) respectively.	22
5	Plots of spin frequency $\nu(t)$ and its derivatives $\dot{\nu}(t), \ddot{\nu}(t)$ versus time for the pulsar J0942-5552 (top) and the Vela pulsar (bottom).	23
6	Comparison between the PSD for the spin frequency in equation (52), the red solid line, and the PSD obtained from the discrete Fourier transform of simulated data (green curve). The green curve has been extracted from a single realization. The corner frequency is indicated by the blue dashed lines. The vertical dashed lines correspond to the first non-DC frequency $\nu_0 = 2\pi/T$, for $T = 20 \text{ yr}$, and to a sampling frequency of 1 data point per day, $\nu_s = 2\pi/(1 \text{ day})$, which defines the observational window. Upper panel corresponds to the Vela pulsar and the lower panel corresponds to the pulsar J0942-5552.	24
7	Comparison between the PSD for the first derivative of spin frequency in equation (52), the red solid line, and the PSD obtained from the discrete Fourier transform of simulated data (green curve) from a single realization for the pulsar J0942-5552. The parameters used have been listed in Table 2, along with the timing noise amplitude $\sigma_{\dot{\nu}}^2 = 2.5 \times 10^{-50} \text{ Hz}^2\text{s}^{-5}$	25
8	$P - \dot{P}$ diagram of the pulsar J0942-5552 (top) and the Vela pulsar (bottom) computed for a timespan of 1000 years. The parameters used have been listed in Table 2, along with the timing noise amplitude $\sigma_{\dot{\nu}}^2 = 2.5 \times 10^{-50} \text{ Hz}^2\text{s}^{-5}$	26

1 Introduction

1.1 Discovery of Pulsars

In 1967, a team of Cambridge astronomers led by Anthony Hewish identified astronomical entities emitting regular pulses of radio waves, a groundbreaking observation that significantly influenced subsequent astrophysical research. This impact was followed by the recognition of Hewish with the Nobel Prize in 1974 for his pioneering work in radio astrophysics. His PhD student, Jocelyn Bell Burnell, made a significant contribution to the discovery by noticing and recognizing the authentic astrophysical nature of the first pulsar signal.

Before this finding, several theorists, including Baade and Zwicky in 1934 and Oppenheimer and Volkoff in 1939, predicted that stable equilibrium stars would be denser than white dwarfs. It was also postulated that these objects may arise due to supernova explosions ([Baade and Zwicky 1934](#)). There was speculation that these objects might initially exhibit rapid rotation, accompanied by strong magnetic fields, with suggestions that the Crab Nebula's energy source could be a rotating neutron star. A rudimentary magnetic dipole model, capable of converting the rotational energy of a neutron star into electromagnetic radiation and subsequent particle motions, had been outlined in literature before the detection.

The announcement of the discovery of a 1.377 s radio pulsar at 81.5 MHz by ([Hewish et al. 1968](#)) did not occur without prior theoretical supposition. Initially, most astrophysicists did not immediately associate pulsars with neutron stars. It was argued for the first time that observed pulsars were rotating neutron stars with surface magnetic fields of approximately 10^{12} G ([T. Gold 1968](#)). Gold suggested that such objects could explain many pulsar features, including the stable pulse period. He predicted a gradual increase in the period as pulsars lost rotational energy, a concept supported by the subsequent discovery of the Crab pulsar's slowdown. In 1969, He demonstrated that the implied energy loss matched the energy required to sustain the Crab nebula ([Thomas Gold 1969](#)). This success, coupled with the shortcomings of alternative models, led to the widespread acceptance of the neutron star model.

1.2 Dynamics of Pulsars

Pulsars are rotating and intensely magnetized neutron stars that emit beamed radiation, much like a lighthouse. They originate from supernova explosions in massive stars. As these neutron stars spin, charged particles (electrons and positrons) in the magnetosphere arrange and oscillate to create a radio beam. The pulse repetition period corresponds directly to the rotation period of the neutron stars. In fact, this accelerated particle motion results in the emission of electromagnetic radiation, with radio frequencies being the most detectable. In the following subsections, we will be elucidating the dynamics of pulsars using the simplest dipole model in more detail by discussing the dipole radiation, energy loss due to rotation, and equations of motions in terms of rotational period and its derivative.

1.2.1 Energy Loss due to Rotations

To consider the energy loss in neutron stars, we can approximate neutron stars to be perfectly spherical for mathematical convenience. Then the rotational energy is given by

$$E = \frac{1}{2}I\Omega^2, \quad (1)$$

where Ω is the angular frequency and I is the moment of inertia. For an incompressible homogeneous sphere of mass M and radius R , the moment of inertia can be written as

$$I = \frac{2}{5}MR^2. \quad (2)$$

For instance, a neutron star of mass $M = 1.2M_\odot$ where M_\odot is the solar mass, and a radius of $R = 10$ km, the moment of inertia is given by

$$I = \frac{2}{5} \times MR^2 \approx 10^{38} \text{ kg m}^2. \quad (3)$$

Assuming a constant moment of inertia, the rotational energy loss can be written as

$$\dot{E} \equiv -\frac{dE}{dt} = -I\Omega\dot{\Omega}, \quad (4)$$

where the dot represents the derivative with respect to time. We can express equation (4) in terms of period ($P = 2\pi/\Omega$) and period derivative ($\dot{P} = -2\pi\dot{\Omega}/\Omega^2$) as

$$\dot{E} = -I \frac{4\pi^2}{P^3} \dot{P}. \quad (5)$$

As the pulsar loses part of its rotational kinetic energy because of electromagnetic radiation, it begins to spin down: the phenomenon of spinning down of pulsars has empirical foundations in the famous Larmor formula (for electromagnetic radiation) or in the Einstein quadrupole formula for gravitational wave emission. Whatever the kind of radiation emitted (electromagnetic or gravitational), this process is known as the “braking” of pulsars. Finally, equation (5) also describes the physical observable known as the spin-down “luminosity”, namely the power radiated at the expense of the rotational kinetic energy of the neutron star.

1.2.2 Magnetic fields and dipole radiation

The Sun and numerous other stars have magnetic fields that are roughly dipolar. Within stellar interiors, where ionization is complete, creating effective electrical conductors, charged particles are restricted to travel along magnetic field lines. Whenever a typical star of radius $R \sim 10^6$ km collapses as a result of a supernova to become a neutron star, the radius decreases to be roughly 10 km. Similarly, the magnetic field strength of scale $B \sim 100$ G becomes $B \sim 10^{12}$ G. Thus, it can be inferred that young neutron stars exhibit a strong magnetic dipolar nature. The power radiated can be considered as the electromagnetic emission from the magnetized rotating neutron star. We make use of the Larmor formula to express the power radiated by a rotating electric dipole.

$$P_{\text{rad}} = \frac{2q^2\dot{v}^2}{3c^3} = \frac{2}{3} \frac{(q\ddot{r} \sin \alpha)^2}{c^3} = \frac{2}{3} \frac{(\ddot{p}_{\perp})^2}{c^3}, \quad (6)$$

where p_{\perp} is the component of the electric dipole moment perpendicular to the rotation axis. Larmor formula is also valid for a magnetic dipole and the power

radiated can be expressed as,

$$P_{\text{rad}} = \frac{2}{3} \frac{(\ddot{m}_{\perp})^2}{c^3}. \quad (7)$$

For a uniformly magnetized sphere with radius R and surface magnetic field strength B , the magnitude of the magnetic dipole moment is

$$m = BR^3. \quad (8)$$

If the inclined magnetic dipole rotates with angular velocity Ω , then using the equations (7) and (8), we can write,

$$P_{\text{rad}} = \frac{2}{3} \frac{m_{\perp}^2 \Omega^4}{c^3} = \frac{2}{3c^3} (BR^3 \sin \alpha)^2 \Omega^4, \quad (9)$$

where α is the inclination angle. Since the equations (4) and (9) represent the rotational energy loss of the pulsar,

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{E} &= -P_{\text{rad}}, \\ -I\Omega\dot{\Omega} &= -\frac{2}{3c^3} B^2 R^6 \Omega^4 \sin^2 \alpha. \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

By solving for B in terms of the P and \dot{P} we retrieve the following expression.

$$B = \sqrt{\frac{3c^3 I}{8\pi^2 R^6 \sin^2 \alpha} P \dot{P}}. \quad (11)$$

1.2.3 Power law and braking index

The equivalence of radiated power emission through dipole and energy loss due to the rotation of neutron stars allows us to express the dynamics in the form of a basic differential equation.

$$\dot{\Omega} = -K\Omega^3, \quad K = \frac{2B^2 R^6 \sin^2 2\alpha}{3c^3 I}, \quad (12)$$

where K is almost constant over many years. The equation (12) can be solved for time t and one can reach the following result

$$t = \frac{1}{2K\Omega^2} \left(1 - \frac{\Omega^2}{\Omega_0^2} \right), \quad (13)$$

where Ω_0 is the frequency of the pulsar at $t = 0$ (when pulsar came into being). However, pulsar spinning fast at $t = 0$ could lead to having the second term in equation (13) to be negligible ($\Omega_0 \gg \Omega$).

$$t = \frac{1}{2K\Omega^2}, \quad (14)$$

Using equation (12) in terms of K and using it in equation (14), the expression for characteristic age in the context of P and \dot{P} can be defined.

$$\tau = \frac{P}{2\dot{P}}. \quad (15)$$

More generally, the spin-down of a pulsar can be expressed as

$$\dot{\Omega} = -K\Omega^n, \quad (16)$$

where n is called the braking index. For example, if the spin-down is dominated by an outward-flowing wind, the value of n is 1, $n = 3$ if dominated by a magnetic dipole, and $n = 5$ if dominated by a magnetic quadrupole.

1.3 $P - \dot{P}$ diagram

Once the data regarding the period and the period derivative of a pulsar are known, it can be placed in a $P - \dot{P}$ diagram. The location of radio pulsars in this plane has been a key diagnostic tool since the early days of pulsar astronomy. Figure (1) shows a $P - \dot{P}$ diagram containing information of about 2000 known pulsars.

The data of known pulsars are stored in the Australia Telescope National Facility (ATNF) database (Manchester et al. 2005). It is to be noted that young pulsars (with low P and high \dot{P}) live in the top-left part of the diagram. The pulsars with the high magnetic field (magnetars) can be found in the top-right of the diagram. The bottom left population of pulsars is known as milliseconds pulsars or recycled pulsars. Millisecond pulsars are distinguished by their extraordinarily quick spin, which normally lasts between a few milliseconds to tens of milliseconds. This fast spinning is caused by accretion, which occurs when a pulsar gains mass from a partner star in a binary system. As material from the companion star spirals onto the pulsar, it transfers angular momentum, increasing the pulsar's rotational speed. This intriguing

evolutionary journey takes these pulsars from relatively slow-rotating neutron stars to the high-speed wonders we see today.

Figure 1: We plot the $P - \dot{P}$ diagram for about 2000 known pulsars listed in the ATNF catalogue. The lines of constant τ are in red, and the lines of constant B are in blue. Pulsars part of a binary system are not plotted.

1.4 Timing Noise

Young neutron stars offer unique insights into astrophysics that differ from the majority of the pulsar population. They frequently display two distinct

deviations from a consistent spin-down behaviour, known as glitches and timing noise. Glitches manifest as sudden leaps in the pulsar’s spin frequency, serving as probes into the interiors of neutron stars. Timing noise, on the other hand, is a form of rotational irregularity causing pulse arrival times to randomly fluctuate around a steady spin-down state. Our sample represents pulsars undergoing rapid spin-down, providing a promising avenue for in-depth studies on timing noise, glitches, and their spin-down patterns.

Pulsar timing, as a technique, facilitates precise measurements of spin periods (P) and spin-down rates (\dot{P}), enabling the exploration of their evolution in the $P - \dot{P}$ diagram, as depicted in Figure 1. Although young pulsar timing presents numerous opportunities to delve into various astrophysical phenomena, it poses a formidable challenge due to the dominance or bias introduced by timing noise and glitches on most of these astrophysical signals. Therefore, a meticulous methodology is imperative in the analysis of young pulsar timing data to distinguish deterministic processes from stochastic components.

For instance, young pulsars are thought to be associated with supernova remnants, and measuring their proper motion allows us to explore the linkages between the neutron star and its progenitor, which has consequences for birthrate statistics. Accurate modelling of timing noise in pulse arrival times is crucial for obtaining unbiased measurements of proper motion through pulsar timing.

2 Stochastic models for timing noise

Timing noise was initially noticed in the Crab pulsar. In order to elucidate the timing noise in the Crab pulsar, it was depicted as random walks either in the phase, frequency, or spin-down parameter of the pulsar (Boynton et al. 1972). Later on, it was shown to be the common characteristic of pulsars (Helfand et al. 1980). Timing noise appears as a red-noise process in the Time of Arrivals (ToAs), suggesting an auto-correlated process lasting months to years. Observations show that pulsars do not precisely diffuse into the $P - \dot{P}$ diagram using the deterministic braking law, but rather wander about it stochastically. This wandering in pulsar evolution is generally characterized by a wide-sense stationary stochastic signal (Groth 1975). After this, numerous endeavours have been made to scrutinize timing noise in pulsars across

extended data spans and for a more extensive pulsar sample. Researchers explored the timing behaviour of 50 pulsars, discovering that timing activity exhibited 50% correlation with \dot{P} but only a weak correlation with P (J. M. Cordes and Helfand 1980). In the spirit of previous work, we have considered timing noise models, analyzed them analytically, and computed observational features numerically.

2.1 Deterministic and stochastic torques

Pulsar timing noise is commonly understood as a random fluctuation in the rotation rate of a neutron star and its associated magnetosphere. This variability must stem from some fluctuating torque, which can broadly be categorized into two sources: external torque, such as radiation torque in the case of pulsars, and internal torque that may originate from the interaction between the neutron star crust and a faster-spinning superfluid component within the star's interior. Whether the erratic spin behaviour is influenced by external or internal torques, studying the system's response offers insight into the internal structure of neutron stars.

The general model for studying the spin wandering of the phase due to the fluctuations in the internal and external torques is formulated in terms of stochastic differential equations. It is realized by considering an extension of the Baym model (Baym et al. 1969) for $m + 1$ rigid internal components:

$$\Omega_t = (\Omega_p(t), \Omega_1(t), \dots, \Omega_m(t)), \quad (17)$$

where Ω_p is the observable component of the angular velocity, depicting the velocity induced by the rotation of the normal matter in the neutron star and magnetosphere. The m components of the angular velocity represent the internal superfluid components of the star that are not strongly coupled to the normal component or the magnetosphere. These superfluids could be either different types of species or the same species co-existing together in the overall structure of the neutron stars. Similarly, as expected, these $m + 1$ superfluid components contributes to the fraction $\mathbf{x} = (x_p, x_1, \dots, x_m)$ of total moment of inertia. However, only m components are independent physically because we are not interested in the possible phenomenon of starquakes, meaning that the

sum of all the fractions must be constant:

$$\sum_{i=1\dots m} x_i = 1 - x_p. \quad (18)$$

In the above equation, x_p is the fraction of the total moment of inertia associated with the observable component of the star, namely the normal or superfluid components that are rigidly coupled to (or strongly coupled with) the magnetosphere. With no emphasis on the nature of internal torque, the total angular momentum $L(t) = \mathbf{x}^\top \cdot \boldsymbol{\Omega}$ is only affected by the influence of external torque. Here, \top represents the matrix transpose. Formally, the decrease in the total angular momentum of the star due to the braking torque is

$$\dot{L} = \mathbf{x}^\top \cdot \dot{\boldsymbol{\Omega}}. \quad (19)$$

The equation (19) can be decomposed into deterministic and fluctuating parts by consideration of stochasticity in the braking torque due to either electromagnetic or gravitational origin.

$$\dot{L} = \mathcal{T}_\infty + \eta_t^\infty, \quad (20)$$

\mathcal{T}_∞ defining the deterministic component and η_t^∞ showing the stochastic part involved in the pulsar dynamics. The pulsar evolution can be modelled through stochastic differential equations such as an Itô equation of the kind

$$d\boldsymbol{\Omega}_t = (B\boldsymbol{\Omega}_t + \mathbf{A}_t)dt + M d\mathbf{W}_t, \quad (21)$$

where B and M are $(m+1) \times (m+1)$ real matrices and \mathbf{A}_t is a real vector describing braking torque which could also involve time dependency. And $d\mathbf{W}_t$ is $(m+1)$ dimensional Wiener process (e.g. random processes which are stationary with independent increments and have zero mean with variance t). The Wiener matrix allows us to model the stochasticity in the external and internal torques. The equation (21) should satisfy the physical constraints: it should satisfy equations (19) and (20), and there should be no internal friction between the components having the same angular velocity. Therefore, equation

(21) can be written in the analogous Langevin form

$$\dot{\boldsymbol{\Omega}}_t = B\boldsymbol{\Omega}_t + \mathbf{A}_t + M\dot{\mathbf{W}}_t, \quad (22)$$

where $\dot{\mathbf{W}}_t$ is white noise and can be described as the derivative of the standard Wiener process ($d\mathbf{W}_t = \dot{\mathbf{W}}_t dt$). White noise is a sequence of uncorrelated random variables with zero mean and finite variance.

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \dot{\mathbf{W}}_t \rangle &= 0 \\ \langle \dot{W}_t^i \dot{W}_s^j \rangle &= \delta_{ij} \delta(t - s). \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

Matrices \mathbf{A}_t , B , and M cannot be chosen independently as general Itô process described by equation (21) should follow the physical constraint.

$$\mathbf{x}^\top \cdot (B\boldsymbol{\Omega}_t + \mathbf{A}_t + M\dot{\mathbf{W}}_t) = \mathcal{T}_\infty + \eta_t^\infty. \quad (24)$$

The equation (24) implies that internal torque should satisfy the action-reaction law. It means that \mathbf{x} should be null left eigenvector of B ($B^\top \mathbf{x} = 0$). Otherwise, the equations (19 and 20) will be violated. Therefore, the total external torque can be written down as

$$\mathbf{x}^\top \cdot \mathbf{A}_t = \mathcal{T}_\infty, \quad (25)$$

$$\mathbf{x}^\top M\dot{\mathbf{W}}_t = \eta_t^\infty. \quad (26)$$

2.1.1 Brownian Model

The simplistic model can be extracted from the generalized methodology developed in the previous section. This model will contain only one component ($m = 0$), which specifies that the star is rotating as a rigid rotor (Antonelli, Basu, and Haskell 2023). Rigid rotor specification enforces the parameter $B = 0$, and the Langevin equation takes the following form,

$$\dot{\boldsymbol{\Omega}}_t = \mathbf{A}_t + M\dot{\mathbf{W}}_t, \quad (27)$$

here M takes the form $M = \sigma_\infty$. As a consequence of taking a rigid rotor schematic, the moment of inertia considered in equation (18) will become

$x_p = 1$ leading us to the simpler form of angular momentum.

$$L(t) = \Omega_p. \quad (28)$$

The prescription to set the strength of the noise in the external torque is as follows. We begin by setting the amplitude of fluctuations in the external torque. Consider a generic force $F = F_0 + \delta F$, where F_0 is deterministic and δF is a white noise process. The physical timescale T_F is defined such that F_0 drives the evolution of the system on the timescales of the order of T_F . We can set the strength of δF by imposing that its effect, over a time interval of order T_F , is a fraction $0 < \alpha < 1$ of the one produced by the deterministic part F_0 (Antonelli, Basu, and Haskell 2023),

$$\int_0^{T_F} \delta F(t) dt \approx \alpha \int_0^{T_F} F_0(t) dt. \quad (29)$$

The above expression is just to provide an overall idea of how to set the strength of fluctuations and is not formally right. As one may notice, the left-hand side of (29) is a random variable and is typically realized within a few standard deviations from its statistical expectation (that is zero). Hence, a more rigorous approach would be to set,

$$\text{std. dev.} \left[\int_0^{T_F} \delta F(t) dt \right] \approx \alpha \int_0^{T_F} F_0(t) dt. \quad (30)$$

In essence, we have parametrized the noise strength in terms of the fraction α . In order to estimate the standard deviation mentioned in (30) we use the property of the Wiener process,

$$W_{t+\Delta t}^i - W_t^i \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sqrt{\Delta t}) \quad \forall i, \Delta t > 0. \quad (31)$$

For pulsars, the relevant timescale is their life timescale $T = \Omega/\dot{\Omega}$. Using the properties (30) and (31), we can write,

$$\sigma_\infty(W_{t+T}^\infty - W_t^\infty) \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_\infty \sqrt{T}). \quad (32)$$

And we require that the standard deviation of this process is a fraction of the

angular velocity Ω ,

$$\sigma_\infty \sqrt{T} = \alpha \Omega, \quad (33)$$

$$\sigma_\infty^2 = \alpha^2 \Omega \dot{\Omega}. \quad (34)$$

The spectrum evaluated by the evolution of pulsars following the dynamics mentioned in this section will effectively be Brownian in nature. The Power Spectral Density (PSD) and instances in the context of pulsars are established in the subsequent sections.

2.1.2 The recent Vargas and Melatos stochastic model

Vargas and Melatos developed a well-motivated model (Vargas and Melatos 2023) by taking the general features of the timing noise model (as mentioned in the previous section) with more interesting features than mere Brownian noise. The spin-down evolution is characterized by four independent variables: the rotational phase ($\phi(t)$), the rotational frequency $\nu(t)$ and its derivatives $\dot{\nu}(t)$ and $\ddot{\nu}(t)$. These dynamical variables are enclosed together in a column vector.

$$\mathbf{X} = (X_1, X_2, X_3, X_4)^\top = (\phi, \nu, \dot{\nu}, \ddot{\nu})^\top. \quad (35)$$

The state vector \mathbf{X} evolves under the action of deterministic and stochastic torques. The deterministic torque, in this case, is of electromagnetic origin where $n = 3$ (see equation (16)) (Gunn and Ostriker 1969) is taken. One is free to entertain other types of deterministic torques such as mass quadruple gravitational radiation ($n = 5$) (Thorne 1980). The stochastic torque defines the peculiar difference between the model discussed previously and the Vargas model. The stochasticity, in this model, is induced phenomenologically by the white noise Langevin driver in $\ddot{\nu}(t)$. However, in the previous section, we were considering the noise to be attached to the $\dot{\Omega}(t)$. Whereas, this model also permits the noise to be added either to the $\dot{\Omega}(t)$ or $\Omega(t)$, according to the context in which the system of compact stars is being investigated. The white noise in $\ddot{\nu}(t)$ generates red noise in $\phi(t)$, $\nu(t)$, and $\dot{\nu}(t)$. The relationship between frequency $\nu(t)$ and angular frequency $\Omega(t)$ is $\Omega(t) = 2\pi\nu(t)$. The calibration is done into white noise driver $\ddot{\nu}(t)$ to generate the phase residuals which resemble the ones produced by the data of real pulsars. Eventually,

we can write the complete model carried out by four simultaneous stochastic differential equations.

$$d\mathbf{X} = (\mathbf{A}\mathbf{X} + \mathbf{E})dt + \Sigma d\mathbf{B}(t), \quad (36)$$

with

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -\gamma_\nu & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -\gamma_{\dot{\nu}} & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -\gamma_{\ddot{\nu}} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (37)$$

$$E = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ \gamma_\nu \nu_{\text{em}}(t) \\ \gamma_{\dot{\nu}} \dot{\nu}_{\text{em}}(t) \\ \ddot{\nu}_{\text{em}}(t) + \gamma_{\ddot{\nu}} \ddot{\nu}_{\text{em}}(t) \end{pmatrix}, \quad (38)$$

and the fluctuating part of the Langevin matrix equation,

$$\Sigma = \text{diag}(0, 0, 0, \sigma_{\ddot{\nu}}), \quad (39)$$

where in $\nu_{\text{em}}(t)$ and its derivatives, subscript 'em' describes that we are taking the deterministic electromagnetic braking law (i.e., $\dot{\nu}_{\text{em}}(t) = K\nu_{\text{em}}^n(t)$). In equations (37) and (38), γ_ν , $\gamma_{\dot{\nu}}$, and $\gamma_{\ddot{\nu}}$ are damping coefficients. $d\mathbf{B}(t)$ is the infinitesimal Wiener increment of zero mean and unit variance. It is important to note that this model is phenomenologically driven and aims to produce the qualitative phenomenon of the typical pulsars. To solve these equations, we can write the right-hand side of these Langevin equations.

$$\frac{d\phi(t)}{dt} = \nu(t), \quad (40)$$

$$\frac{d\nu(t)}{dt} = -\gamma_\nu[\nu(t) - \nu_{\text{em}}(t)] + \dot{\nu}(t), \quad (41)$$

$$\frac{d\dot{\nu}(t)}{dt} = -\gamma_{\dot{\nu}}[\dot{\nu}(t) - \dot{\nu}_{\text{em}}(t)] + \ddot{\nu}(t), \quad (42)$$

$$\frac{d\ddot{\nu}(t)}{dt} = -\gamma_{\ddot{\nu}}[\ddot{\nu}(t) - \ddot{\nu}_{\text{em}}(t)] + \ddot{\nu}_{\text{em}}(t) + \xi(t), \quad (43)$$

where $\xi(t)$ is a white noise driver with the following properties.

$$\begin{aligned}\langle \xi(t) \rangle &= 0 \\ \langle \xi(t)\xi(t') \rangle &= \sigma_{\dot{\nu}}^2 \delta(t - t').\end{aligned}\tag{44}$$

For instance, (41) describes a relaxation process, in which $\nu(t)$ reverts to the mean $\nu_{\text{em}}(t)$ on a time-scale γ_{ν}^{-1} . The process is driven by the stochastic torque $\dot{\nu}(t)$, which inherits its randomness from the integration of the white-noise driver with amplitude $\sigma_{\dot{\nu}}$ mentioned in (39). It is important to note that the phase can be obtained by integrating the equation (40).

$$\phi(t) = \phi(0) + \int_0^t dt' \nu(t').\tag{45}$$

The initial phase is just a historical coincidence and can be taken as $\phi(0) = 0$. The behaviour of damping coefficients is constrained to be in the defined astrophysical regime: $\gamma_{\nu} \sim \gamma_{\dot{\nu}} \ll T_{\text{obs}}^{-1} \ll \gamma_{\dot{\nu}}$. Here, T_{obs} is the total observation time. It is vital to highlight that the real paper by Vargas and Melatos includes a typo in the equation (39). They have written it as $\sigma_{\dot{\nu}}^2$ instead of $\sigma_{\dot{\nu}}$. The analysis of equation (43) justifies that $\eta(t)$ is a white noise driver and analogous to the $\sigma_{\dot{\nu}}$.

2.2 Power Spectral Density

Our derivation of the Power Spectral Density (PSD) is based on the trick of computing the Fourier transform of the Langevin equation. We begin by introducing the Fourier representation (Rice 1944),

$$\delta\Omega_t = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{i\omega t} \delta\Omega_{\omega} \frac{d\omega}{2\pi}.\tag{46}$$

In general, one can define the matrix

$$P(\omega, \omega') = \left\langle \delta\Omega_{\omega} \delta\Omega_{\omega'}^{\dagger} \right\rangle,\tag{47}$$

where $\delta\Omega_\omega^\dagger$ is the conjugate transpose of $\delta\Omega_\omega$. From the Langevin equation in (27), we have,

$$\delta\Omega_\omega = (i\omega\mathbb{I} - B)^{-1}M\dot{\mathbf{W}}_\omega. \quad (48)$$

$$\delta\Omega_\omega^\dagger = (-i\omega'\mathbb{I} - B^T)^{-1}M^T\dot{\mathbf{W}}_{\omega'}. \quad (49)$$

Along with the properties of Wiener processes mentioned in (23), we can calculate the matrix in (47). We are only interested in the PSD of the observable component which is given by,

$$P_p(\omega) = [(i\omega\mathbb{I} - B)^{-1}MM^T(-i\omega\mathbb{I} - B^T)^{-1}]_{pp}. \quad (50)$$

The subscript pp indicates that only the $i = j = p$ component of the matrix is considered. Note that this expression of PSD is applicable for any Langevin equation expressed in the form of (27). For the Brownian model, equation (50) reduces to

$$P_p(\omega) = \frac{\sigma_\infty^2}{\omega^2}. \quad (51)$$

In the case of the Vargas model, the PSD can be obtained for each of the components $\phi, \nu, \dot{\nu}, \ddot{\nu}$ and can be calculated analytically in a similar manner.

$$P_p(\omega) = \begin{cases} \frac{\sigma^2}{\omega^2(\omega^2 + \gamma_\nu^2)(\omega^2 + \gamma_{\dot{\nu}}^2)(\omega^2 + \gamma_{\ddot{\nu}}^2)} & \text{for } \phi, \\ \frac{\sigma^2}{(\omega^2 + \gamma_\nu^2)(\omega^2 + \gamma_{\dot{\nu}}^2)(\omega^2 + \gamma_{\ddot{\nu}}^2)} & \text{for } \nu, \\ \frac{\sigma^2}{(\omega^2 + \gamma_{\dot{\nu}}^2)(\omega^2 + \gamma_{\ddot{\nu}}^2)} & \text{for } \dot{\nu}, \\ \frac{\sigma^2}{(\omega^2 + \gamma_{\ddot{\nu}}^2)} & \text{for } \ddot{\nu} \end{cases} \quad (52)$$

While moving from the Brownian model to the Vargas model, we observe the presence of a spectral turnover in the PSDs calculated using the latter. For instance, the PSD of ν ($P_\nu(\omega)$) exhibits the following behaviour. The

frequencies $\gamma_\nu, \gamma_{\dot{\nu}}, \gamma_{\ddot{\nu}}$ play the role of corner frequencies.

$$P_\nu(\omega) \propto \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\omega^2} & : \gamma_\nu < \omega < \gamma_{\dot{\nu}} \\ \frac{1}{\omega^4} & : \gamma_{\dot{\nu}} < \omega < \gamma_{\ddot{\nu}} \\ \frac{1}{\omega^6} & : \omega > \gamma_{\ddot{\nu}} \end{cases} \quad (53)$$

In computational terms, the power spectral density (PSD) can be calculated from the residuals by means of the Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT). We have used the algorithm of Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) to perform the DFT. For the signal Ω_p , sampled at times $t_l = lT/N$ for $l = 0, 1, \dots, N-1$, the definition of DFT is ([Antonelli, Basu, and Haskell 2023](#)),

$$\delta\tilde{\Omega}_p(\omega_k) = \sum_{l=0}^{N-1} \delta\tilde{\Omega}_p(t_l) e^{-2\pi i l k / N}, \quad (54)$$

$$\omega_k = k\nu_s. \quad (55)$$

where T is the time span of the signal, $\nu_0 = 2\pi/T$ is the first non-DC frequency and $\nu_s = 2\pi N/T$ is the sampling frequency.

3 Numerical simulations of the Brownian and Vargas models

We now present the results obtained by using the models described in the previous section. The models have been implemented in Python. The stochastic differential equations have been numerically solved using the publicly available Python package *sdeint* ([Aburn 2017](#)). The pulsars considered in this report are PSR J0835-4510 (commonly known as the Vela pulsar) and PSR-J0942-5552 ([Lower et al. 2020](#)).

3.1 Brownian Model

Using the mathematical model in (27), we create a random realization of data by solving them with the rotational parameters of the Vela pulsar and PSR J0942-5552. As mentioned earlier, the model only considers the

fluctuations in the external torque. This model has been implemented using both the *sdeint* package and by the Euler-Maruyama scheme (appendix C) and has been found to give consistent results. Figure 2 show the evolution of the above pulsars over 20 years. A general trend is found where the younger pulsars have larger timing noise than the older ones in accordance with the observations (Shannon and James M Cordes 2010).

Parameter	Units	Vela	PSR J0942-5552
$\nu(t)$	Hz	11.1946499395	1.50514304056
$\dot{\nu}(t)$	Hz s ⁻¹	-1.5666×10^{-11}	-51.376×10^{-15}
Age	yr	1.13×10^4	4.64×10^5
α	-	10^{-3}	10^{-2}

Table 1: Parameters for the two pulsars used in the Brownian model

Figure 2: The angular velocity of the Vela pulsar (left) and the pulsar J0942-5552 (right) vs time. The parameters used to generate the plots have been listed in Table 1.

The PSD calculated from the residuals of angular velocity exhibit $1/\omega^2$ behaviour which coincides with the analytical expression in (51). It is to be noted that this model does not allow to compute $\dot{\Omega}_t$ because it is a degenerate white noise process, meaning that the fluctuations in $\dot{\Omega}_t$ and hence in the \dot{P} are unrealistically large and can not be properly modelled within the Brownian prescription. Therefore we need to consider a model that encodes more correlations and therefore allows us to probe fluctuations also in \dot{P} .

Figure 3: The power spectral densities of the Vela pulsar (left) and the pulsar J0942-5552 (right). The red line is a reference line of slope -2. The dashed black lines indicate the observational window: $\nu_0 = 2\pi/(20 \text{ yr})$, and $\nu_s = 2\pi/(1 \text{ day})$. The parameters used to generate the plots have been listed in Table 1.

3.2 Vargas Model

By solving the system of equations (36) with the initial conditions and parameters given in Table 2, the evolution of the Vela pulsar and the PSR J0942-5552 has been realized for $T_{\text{obs}} = 5$ years.

Parameter	Units	Vela	PSR J0942-5552
$\nu(t)$	Hz	11.1946499395	1.50514304056
$\dot{\nu}(t)$	Hz s ⁻¹	-1.5666×10^{-11}	-51.376×10^{-15}
$\ddot{\nu}(t)$	Hz s ⁻²	1.028×10^{-21}	8×10^{-24}
γ_ν	s ⁻¹	10^{-13}	10^{-13}
$\gamma_{\dot{\nu}}$	s ⁻¹	10^{-13}	10^{-13}
$\gamma_{\ddot{\nu}}$	s ⁻¹	10^{-6}	10^{-6}

Table 2: Initial parameters for the two pulsars used in Vargas model

Figure 5 represent the rotational evolution of the two pulsars. The data is generated following the braking law with $n = 3$ and the timing noise $\sigma_{\dot{\nu}}^2 = 2.5 \times 10^{-50} \text{ Hz}^2 \text{ s}^{-5}$ is set in order to make the synthetic phase residuals resemble qualitatively the real phase residuals (see Figure 4). It has been found that the generated data qualitatively resembles the actual phase residuals.

Figure 4: Actual (left) and few random realizations of the generated (right) timing residuals of the pulsars. Top panel shows the data corresponding to the pulsar J0942-5552 and the bottom panel corresponds to the Vela pulsar. The real data has been extracted from Vargas and Melatos (2023) and Antonelli et.al (2023) respectively.

We apply the prescription mentioned in (54) to the residuals of the parameters of the model to compute their power spectral densities. The PSD of the spin frequency undergoes a spectral turnover from -4 to -6 at the frequency $\gamma_{\dot{\nu}}$. We manage to see the presence of a corner frequency within the observational window. The PSD extracted from a single realization (that is always the case for real timing data) is considerably more noisy, but is in agreement with the PSD calculated theoretically. Corner frequencies act as boundaries that would indicate the dominance of certain physical processes acting on the pulsar, on certain timescales. It is to be further investigated as to which physical process dominates in these individual timeframes.

Figure 5: Plots of spin frequency $\nu(t)$ and its derivatives $\dot{\nu}(t)$, $\ddot{\nu}(t)$ versus time for the pulsar J0942-5552 (top) and the Vela pulsar (bottom).

Figure 6: Comparison between the PSD for the spin frequency in equation (52), the red solid line, and the PSD obtained from the discrete Fourier transform of simulated data (green curve). The green curve has been extracted from a single realization. The corner frequency is indicated by the blue dashed lines. The vertical dashed lines correspond to the first non-DC frequency $\nu_0 = 2\pi/T$, for $T = 20$ yr, and to a sampling frequency of 1 data point per day, $\nu_s = 2\pi/(1 \text{ day})$, which defines the observational window. Upper panel corresponds to the Vela pulsar and the lower panel corresponds to the pulsar J0942-5552.

Similarly, the PSD of the first derivative of spin frequency also shows a spectral turnover from -2 to -4 (see figure 7). The analytical expressions of

the PSD also indicate the presence of other corner frequencies but they lie at unrealistically large observation timescales (such as an observation every one million years) and are not discussed here.

Figure 7: Comparison between the PSD for the first derivative of spin frequency in equation (52), the red solid line, and the PSD obtained from the discrete Fourier transform of simulated data (green curve) from a single realization for the pulsar J0942-5552. The parameters used have been listed in Table 2, along with the timing noise amplitude $\sigma_{\dot{\nu}}^2 = 2.5 \times 10^{-50} \text{ Hz}^2 \text{ s}^{-5}$.

Figure 8 shows the $P - \dot{P}$ diagram obtained for the Vela and PSR J0942-5552 pulsar computed using the Vargas model. The plot tracks the period and its derivative for 1000 years. The overall spin-down nature is clearly observed and it is to be noted that the presence of noise fluctuates the trajectory of the smooth spin-down caused by the electromagnetic braking only ($n = 3$). To visually track the evolution in a log-log $P - \dot{P}$ diagram similar to the one in the figure 1, more computational power is required.

Figure 8: $P - \dot{P}$ diagram of the pulsar J0942-5552 (top) and the Vela pulsar (bottom) computed for a timespan of 1000 years. The parameters used have been listed in Table 2, along with the timing noise amplitude $\sigma_v^2 = 2.5 \times 10^{-50} \text{ Hz}^2 \text{ s}^{-5}$.

4 Conclusions

Over fifty years after the discovery of the first radio pulsar, their time-evolution remains a source of debate. We have studied the possibility of de-

scribing the timing noise using a Brownian model for the fluctuations in the external torque. However, the Brownian model does not allow tracking the $P - \dot{P}$ of a pulsar as the noise is unrealistically large in the angular frequency and hence in the \dot{P} . Therefore, we moved to the Vargas model which injects timing noise in the second derivative of spin frequency and encodes more correlations that enable us to probe the fluctuations in \dot{P} . This serves as the first step in the study of the diffusion of pulsars in the $P - \dot{P}$ diagram. Our stochastic solver is the foundation for a comprehensive investigation of the diffusion in P and \dot{P} with the Vargas model. We will be able to probe the diffusion process and see if it will cover the current observed population of non-recycled pulsars by solving many stochastic trajectories over many years (of the order of thousands/or more for young pulsars).

It will be interesting to study the timing noise models when multiple sources of noise are incorporated with the different parameters of the model. We can extend the present framework beyond the concept of pure white noise, by including the effect of glitches and their impact on the power spectral densities. We could also analyse the impact of the timing noise in the measurement of the braking index of the pulsars. Further study must be done in the implementation of such models.

5 Prospects

In this work, we have developed a tool – the Python simulations – to study two different timing noise models that are simple enough to be analytically studied. Our numerical Python routine has been tested and validated by the known analytical results of the two models in discussion, the Brownian model and the Vargas and Melatos model. Therefore, our routine may be used for more realistic spin-down models that include non-linear terms, for which the statistical parameters (e.g. the power spectral density) can only be determined numerically rather than analytically: when the system is linear, the Fourier transform tool can be used to extract the exact form of the PSD, making the PSD analysis simple. Furthermore, the developed tool can be used to investigate the secular diffusion of pulsars in the $P - \dot{P}$ diagram and determine whether the stochastic fluctuations produced by the timing noise model(s) are sufficient to reproduce the observed bulk population of non-recycled radio

pulsars.

Appendix

A - Primer on Noise

Noise, in its broadest meaning, refers to any undesirable or random fluctuation in a signal or a system. To start a discussion about noise it's convenient to consider the ubiquitous exponential decay equation:

$$\dot{x}(t) = -\alpha x(t), \quad (\text{A1.1})$$

where $\alpha > 0$ describes relaxation. We can consider noise in the given equation by either adding the random fluctuation or multiplying it with the dynamical variable $x(t)$,

$$\dot{x}(t) = -\alpha x(t) + \eta(t) \quad (\text{A1.2})$$

$$\dot{x}(t) = -(\alpha + \eta(t))x(t) \quad (\text{A1.3})$$

In the above equation, $\eta(t)$ is a random fluctuation, which can be described as a stochastic process that represents noise. The randomness in $\eta(t)$ also makes $x(t)$, a stochastic variable. In fact, solutions to such stochastic differential equations are also stochastic processes. There are different types of noise, but one of the most important and widely used is the so-called “white noise”. broadly speaking, white noise is the most random process one may think of, in which the two instances of white noise, $\eta(t)$ and $\eta(t')$ are completely independent. Thanks to this property, the solution to the systems in which white noise appears is a continuous-time Markov process, meaning that it is a memoryless process (we expand on this point in Appendix B).

The two equations above are quite different from the analysis point of view. The one in (A1.2) is essentially a linear equation plus a noisy forcing term that is additive. In this case, the Fourier transform tool can be used to find the analytical PSD. However, this is not true for equation (A1.3), that is the prototypical example of “multiplicative noise”. Our Python routine also works for stochastic equations with multiplicative noise, so it may be used to study the PSD of non-linear and multiplicative spin-down models.

B - Wiener Process

The Wiener process, named after American mathematician Norbert Wiener, is a mathematical model for a continuous-time stochastic process. The major aspects of the procedure are described as follows:

- 1) The Wiener process has a continuous trajectory over time.
- 2) The increments of the Wiener process over any time interval are stationary, meaning that their statistical properties (such as mean and variance) do not change with time.
- 3) The increments of the Wiener process over disjoint time intervals are independent of each other. This property is crucial in capturing the random and unpredictable nature of the process.
- 4) The increments of the Wiener process are normally distributed (following a Gaussian distribution). Specifically, if Δt is the time increment, then the increment ΔW over that time interval follows a normal distribution with mean 0 and variance proportional to t , $W \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma\sqrt{t})$.
- 5) The Wiener process possesses the Markov property. This means that given its present state, its future behaviour is independent of its past. In other words, the current state encapsulates all relevant information for predicting future behaviour.

For a normal random variable X , the stochastic differential equation associated with the Wiener process $W(t)$ can be expressed as,

$$dW(t) = X\sqrt{dt} \tag{A1.4}$$

C - Euler-Maruyama Scheme

The Euler-Maruyama scheme is a numerical method for approximating the solutions of stochastic differential equations (SDEs). For a general SDE of the form,

$$dX(t) = a(X(t), t)dt + b(X(t), t)dW(t), \tag{A1.5}$$

where $a(X(t), t)dt$ represents the deterministic part and $b(X(t), t)dW(t)$ represents the stochastic part of the equation then the Euler-Maruyama scheme can be

written as,

$$X_{n+1} = X_n + a(X_n, t_n)h + b(X_n, t_n)\Delta W_n, \quad (\text{A1.6})$$

where the subscript X_n is the approximation of the solution at t_n , h is the time-step size and

$$\Delta W_n = W_{n+1} - W_n. \quad (\text{A1.7})$$

For the Brownian model in (27), the Euler-Maruyama scheme is implemented as,

$$\delta\Omega_p^{t+\Delta t} = \delta\Omega_p^t + X_p \frac{\sigma_\infty}{x_p} \sqrt{\Delta t}; \quad X_p \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1) \quad (\text{A1.8})$$

where the shorthand notation $\Omega(t) = \Omega^t$ is used.

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